

Interval Measurement Versus a Continuous Variable in Quantum Entropy Calculations

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. and SPN, Messina Dec. 7, 2023

Physics is concerned with measurements. In fact, we argue that Newtonian mechanics is specifically formulated in terms of measurements in that it uses intervals. For example, speed is dx/dt , i.e. two intervals are used dx and dt , both of which may be measured. A limiting process is taken to make it appear as if the intervals go to 0, but they cannot because one cannot perform a measurement in an interval of 0. Furthermore, if one wishes to use a continuous variable, as in the quantum mechanical free particle wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$, there is no need to introduce an interval.

Thus, it seems that interval based physics is introduced to implicitly account for measurements. This, we argue, carries over into probability. For example, a coin or die is in a particular state which must be measured in an interval of time. This idea of interval of time is carried over into dynamics. A particle moving with a constant velocity is said to have an equal probability to be at any dx because it spends the same dt there. This argument, based on measurement, is based on intervals. One may even extend it to a classical mechanical bound particle by suggesting dt is proportional to the amount of time a particle spends in dx and hence its probability, i.e. $Cdx/v(x)$.

As noted, quantum mechanics is very different. It is not based on intervals, but on a dynamic x variable in the free particle case $\exp(ipx)$. This leads to a dilemma, we argue. X is a measurable associated with an interval dx , but x in $\exp(ipx)$ continuously changes. Thus, it seems that probability associated with x (i.e. an interval one based on the amount of time dt spent in each dx i.e. $P(x,p)dx = dx/L$ where L is length) is one associated with measurement, while x in $\exp(ipx)$ is not directly measurable. In other words, x in $\exp(ipx)$ is not a state like heads up or a number on a die. X measurements must follow from interactions, but these interactions determine the x distribution. For example, two phase shifted $\exp(ipx)$ s may interfere, or one may 2-slit interference, 1 slit diffraction etc. The resulting x pattern, even at the wavefunction level is based on the interaction which occurs and one then takes $W^*(x)W(x)$ to obtain the interval based probability which is apparently linked to measurement. One may see clearly the interval notion in $\int W^*(x)W(x) dx$. One does not write $\int dx \exp(ipx)$ in quantum mechanics. Similar considerations hold for a single particle bound state.

We further argue that an interval picture is like a distributed variable picture, i.e. one has a length and distributes little pieces dx . A continuous x picture, as in $\exp(ipx)$, is dynamic and not based on a distribution of x pieces.

Classical Mechanics

Classical mechanics is often defined in terms of a measurement process. For example:

$$\text{speed} = dx/dt \quad ((1))$$

This suggests one must use an interval dt based on a clock and measure two positions of the particle. That one takes limits such that intervals shrink to zero does not change the fact that one uses an interval based picture, we argue.

This notion of intervals seems to carry over into probability considerations. For example, a classical particle moving through space spends dt in dx , and the interval dt is sometimes taken as being proportional to its probability to be in dx . This leads to:

$$P(x,v)dx = Cdx/v(x) \quad ((2)) \quad \text{where } v(x) \text{ is speed at } x \quad \text{From } ((1)) \text{ } v(x) \text{ is also based on intervals}$$

$$\text{For a constant speed, } P(x,v)dx = dx/L \text{ where } L \text{ is length} \quad ((3))$$

Thus, probabilities are based on measurable intervals and one identifies states within these intervals. For example, the interval dx is associated with the state x (the center point of dx) even though this is not a state at all. The idea is that if one shrinks the interval to 0, then x and dx coincide, but one cannot take measurements in $dx = 0$ intervals.

In other words, classical mechanics seems to be based on chunky intervals which appear to be smooth because they are made small. One does not really deal with continuous variables.

Quantum Free Particle

The quantum free particle, we argue, is something very different as is a photon. It is based on a true continuous variable x in $\exp(ipx)$, its wavefunction. We have argued in previous notes that an interval picture involves frozen out motion because $P(x,p)dx = dx/L$ shows no dynamics associated with p in space. We suggested that:

$$P(x,p) = \exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) \quad ((4))$$

One may see that $\exp(ipx)$ is not associated with an interval at all, but is used to create $P(x,p)$, which is.

We suggest that $\exp(ipx)$ uses a dynamic variable x to deal with a dynamic processes in space which are not described by imposing intervals. Periodicity actually introduces natural intervals \hbar/p . These occur so that different $\exp(ipx)$ values are orthogonal, i.e.

$$\int dx \exp(-ip_1x)\exp(ip_2x) = 0 \text{ unless } p_1 = p_2 \quad ((5))$$

This notion of orthogonality carries over to single particle bound states.

Thus, increasing energy seems to increase information because the wavelength decreases and a high p has high resolution. As a result, there is a built-in information in $\exp(ipx)$, but this does not seem to be directly used in a Shannon's entropy calculation, which is based on information, because there is no interval -measurement picture. One must use $\exp(ipx)$ in various interactions which leads to a $W(x)$ distributed in space and then take $W^*(x)W(x)$ which returns to the interval scenario in order to calculate Shannon's entropy. It is, however, $\exp(ipx)$, with its continuous x , which is responsible for the physical results. The interval scenario is simply convenient for measurements.

Quantum Single Particle Bound State

A quantum single particle bound state is interesting. $\exp(ipx)$ describes continuous motion in x and hence describes interactions correctly. In such a case, one creates a wavefunction:

$$W(x) = \sum \text{over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx) \quad ((6))$$

It is the basis functions $\exp(ipx)$ divided by $W(x)$ which become the dynamic probabilities used to calculate average kinetic energy, because physically interactions occur following $\exp(ipx)$. One may see that $W(x)$ is a function in x and that it contains weights associated with p , namely $a(p)$. In order to create probabilities in the interval world, one uses:

$$P(x) = W^*(x)W(x) \quad ((7A)) \text{ and } P(p) = a^*(p)a(p) \quad ((7B))$$

These are then used in Shannon's entropy calculations in the literature. They are based on intervals dx and dp which are used in normalization, and intervals are associated with measurement.

Intervals and a Distributed Variable

We have suggested that intervals are associated with measurements, but they are also linked with distributed variables. For example, if one uses dx , one is using a portion of L . Thus, we argue that an interval based picture is related to a distributed variable one. A Maxwell-Boltzmann gas is based on a distributed variable picture as one assigns e_i (energy) values from a total energy E . On the other hand, one may use the maximization of Shannon's entropy using continuous variable p and x , with no notion of a distributed variable and hence no overall parameter like T , temperature, which is associated with such a distribution.

Extremizing $-P(x,p) \ln(P(x,p) + ipx P(x,p))$ ((8)) yields $\exp(ipx)$ with p and x as continuous variables.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggest that interval based physics, i.e. Newtonian mechanics, is linked directly to measurement. This may even be carried over to notions of probability as the interval dt is said to be proportional to the amount of time a particle spends in dx , i.e. the probability to be at dx . This leads to $P(x,p)dx = dx/L$.

Motion, however, is dynamical and cycles through all x points. We suggest that there is a priori no reason to use intervals. Rather a continuous x should be used, which is what is done for a free particle wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$. There is no notion of dx associated with $\exp(ipx)$. An issue which occurs is that classical probabilities are often based on states. For example, a coin may be in the state of heads up or down, a die in a state of 1 etc. These states need to be measured in intervals of time. They are not associated with a continuous variable.

Thus, $\exp(ipx)$ seems to be linked with $P(x,p)dx = dx/L$ to associate it with measurement, i.e. $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = 1$. It is $\exp(ipx)$, however, with a continuous x , which governs physical interactions. Given that one has a continuous variable x , interactions govern the x distribution of $\exp(ipx)$, and these give different results, e.g. single slit diffraction, two slit interference. One does not associate an x like one associates a heads up or down. After using a wavefunction, however, to describe an interaction, one returns to the measurement picture which uses intervals. This seems to be why $W^*(x)W(x) = P(x)$ calculations, while the real information is contained in $\exp(ipx)$ s. Nevertheless, information seems to be contained in $\exp(ipx)$ s as the higher p is, the higher the resolution which suggests more information or details about a length L .